

La Sfera Challenge

Team Wellcome

Team Wellcome will use the manuscript at the Wellcome Library, MS 231

TEAM DOCUMENTS

[Transcription Portal](#)

[Project Log](#)

[Rules and Guidelines](#)

TEAM UPDATES:

July 23: And that's a wrap for Team Wellcome! To celebrate, here's a lovely drawing from Wellcome MS 230:

July 19: We'll use this Google doc to resolve the remaining disputed meanings and decide on transcription conventions:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19jrmnAKY3PNE-ST-b8FBSVgYvDAYoK6jZ43S265wals/edit?usp=sharing>

July 18: More wonders from Wellcome MS 230:

July 18: Our scribe is showing a few quirks. He puts little hash marks above his e's, and sometimes his o's, like this:

July 17: Take a look at the fabulous Wellcome MS 230.

July 17: We're off and running this morning, after an organizational meeting on Tuesday, July 14. We're already finding interesting anomalies in the text.

July 10: Team Wellcome is complete!

Stephanie J. Lahey

@SJLahey

Remember [#LaSferaChallenge](#)? Well, we're at it again! [#LaSferaChallenge2](#) will run July 17–31. I'm delighted to announce that I'll be co-captaining the [@WellcomeLibrary](#) team with [@MarieRichards4](#) 📄✍️

lasferachallenge.wordpress.com/team-2/ ✓

[#Manuscripts](#) [#transcription](#) [#palaeography](#) [#DH](#)

July 5: TEAM WELLCOME Co-Captains are busy getting ready! If you want to work with us on this wonderful manuscript please contact us via Twitter DM at [@SJLahey](https://twitter.com/SJLahey) and [@marierichards4](https://twitter.com/marierichards4), or Marie at countessofdia@gmail.com.

TEAM WELLCOME members include:

- Susanna Barsella, Fordham University ([@BarsellaS](https://twitter.com/BarsellaS))
 - Francesco Ciabattini, Georgetown University
 - Izzy DeSantis, The Ohio State University
 - Francesca Giannetti, Rutgers University ([@jo_frankie](https://twitter.com/jo_frankie))
 - Jocelyn Karlan, I Tatti-Harvard ([@jocelynmk1](https://twitter.com/jocelynmk1))
 - Stephanie J. Lahey, University of Victoria, Co-Captain ([@SJLahey](https://twitter.com/SJLahey))
 - Rose McCandless, The Ohio State University
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 - Paul Moffett, Memorial University of Newfoundland ([@DoctorMoffett](https://twitter.com/DoctorMoffett))
 - Marie Richards, Independent Scholar, Co-Captain ([@marierichards4](https://twitter.com/marierichards4))
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